

Review

Bioplastics in agricultural soils: Biodegradability, analytical techniques, and soil microbial impact

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Bioplastics differ strongly in degradation pathways and environmental performance.
- Bibliometric analysis identifies overlooked gaps in key degradation parameters.
- Highlights the need for standardized methods to assess bioplastics in soils.
- Reviews crop, soil, and microbiome responses to realistic bioplastic inputs.
- Biological responses do not necessarily imply functional integration into soil systems.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The use of bioplastics is promoted as an alternative to mitigate plastic pollution in agricultural soils. However, their environmental safety remains insufficiently controlled under realistic agricultural conditions. This review

Abbreviations: Bio-MPs, Biodegradable Microplastics; Bio-PA, Bio-based polyamide; Bio-PC, Bio-based polycarbonate; Bio-PE, Bio-based polyethylene; Bio-PET, Bio-based polyethylene terephthalate; Bio-PP, Bio-based polypropylene; BOD, Biochemical Oxygen Demand; CEC, Cation Exchange Capacity; DOC, Dissolved Organic Carbon; DSC, Differential Scanning Calorimetry; FTIR, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy; GC-MS, Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry; GPC, Gel Permeation Chromatography; HPLC, High-Performance Liquid Chromatographic–Mass Spectrometry; LDPE, Low-Density Polyethylene; LC-MS, Liquid Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry; MBN, Microbial Biomass Nitrogen; MBC, Microbial Biomass Carbon; MPs, Microplastics; NMR, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance; PA, Polyamide; PBAT, Polybutylene Adipate Terephthalate; PBS, PolyButylene succinate; PBSA, PolyButylene succinate-co-adipate; PC, Polycarbonate; PCL, Polycaprolactone; PE, Polyethylene; PET, Polyethylene Terephthalate; PHA, Polyhydroxyalkanoates; PHB, Polyhydroxybutyrate; PHBV, Poly3-Hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate; PLA, Polylactic Acid; PHS, PolyHexamethylene Succinate; PPC, Polypropylene Carbonate; PU, Polyurethane; PVC, Polyvinyl Chloride; PVA, Polyvinyl Alcohol; Py-GC-MS, Pyrolysis–Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry; Raman, Raman Spectroscopy; S-AKP, Soil Alkaline Phosphatase; S-CAT, Soil Catalase Activity; SEM, Scanning Electron Microscopy; SL, Soil Lipids; SOM, Soil Organic Matter; SDHA, Soil Dehydrogenase Activity; TED-GC-MS, Thermal Extraction and Desorption-Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry; TGA, Thermogravimetric Analysis; Tg, Glass Transition Temperature; TPA, Terephthalic Acid; TPS, Thermoplastic Starch; UV, Ultraviolet; XPS, X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy; XRD, X-Ray Diffraction.

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Biodegradation assessment
Microplastic persistence
Environmental risk

critically examines the behavior of bioplastics in agrarian soils by integrating evidence on degradation mechanisms, analytical methodologies, and soil-plant biological responses. Based on a bibliometric analysis and an in-depth study of experimental evidence, we emphasize that commonly applied techniques often capture surface alterations or material disintegration, providing a limited view of the fate of polymer-derived carbon. This methodological bias may lead to overestimating biodegradation rates and environmental safety. Consequently, biodegradable microplastics and other intermediate residues could persist in soils, particularly under repeated seasonal applications. Biological interactions with bioplastics are highly context-dependent and do not necessarily indicate functional integration into soil biogeochemical cycles. Short-term biological responses may show adaptation or physical effects rather than long-term environmental benefits. To address these limitations, we propose an integrative conceptual framework that links degradation pathways, analytical tests, and biological responses, emphasizing that these concepts must be evaluated jointly to enable robust environmental risk assessments. We identify critical knowledge gaps, including insufficient reporting of key experimental parameters, such as temperature, moisture, or material thickness, the lack of data on the final fate of carbon, and limited long-term studies. Overall, this work underscores that biodegradability alone does not ensure environmental safety and highlights the need for risk-oriented and context-aware assessments under realistic agricultural conditions to guide the responsible use of bioplastics in agricultural soils.

1. Introduction

1.1. Plastic contamination in agricultural soils: from conventional plastics to bioplastics

Plastics, owing to their low production cost, light weight, and versatility, are deeply integrated into strategic sectors such as packaging, agriculture, the textile industry, construction, and medicine [1]. Plastic production, first recorded in 1960 [2] with a volume of 0.5 million tons (Mt), has exhibited exponential growth, reaching 430.9 Mt in 2024 [3]. However, the success of this material has led to global dependency, coupled with ineffective waste management, resulting in an unprecedented environmental crisis. Based on 2024 estimates, approximately 52.1 Mt of plastic are released into the environment each year without proper control or management. It is estimated that of the approximately 6300 Mt of plastic waste generated up to 2017, around 4977 Mt have accumulated in landfills or the natural environment [4].

The widespread use of plastics in agriculture, including mulching films, irrigation systems, and agrochemical encapsulation, among others, has contributed to yield stabilization and resource efficiency. However, their persistence in soils has raised growing environmental concerns. Conventional plastics progressively fragment into microplastics (<5 mm), which are now recognized as ubiquitous soil contaminants. Field studies have shown that plastic mulching can result in severe accumulation of macro- and microplastic residues throughout the soil profile, with measurable impacts on soil structure, porosity, nutrient dynamics, and biological activity [5, 6].

At present, agricultural soils constitute the main reservoir of plastic pollution, with contamination levels between 4 and 23 times higher than those reported in marine ecosystems [7]. Mulching films, predominantly manufactured from polyethylene (PE), are a primary source of microplastic (MP) contamination in agricultural soils. A long-term study on agrarian soils exposed to 32 years of continuous mulching film revealed that these materials accounted for up to 56% of the total MPs at depths ranging from 0 to 100 cm, with an average of 8885 particles kg^{-1} in the surface layer (0–10 cm) and 2899 particles kg^{-1} in deeper layers (80–100 cm) [8].

Due to their small size, hydrophobicity, and high surface area, MPs can adsorb organic pollutants and heavy metals, thereby increasing their environmental toxicity and modifying their bioavailability [9]. Experimental studies have demonstrated that the presence of MPs in soil reduces seed germination and plant growth, negatively affects the soil microbial community, and affects soil organism interactions [10], and increases mortality rates while reducing growth and reproduction in macrofauna such as earthworms [11]. These findings have reinforced the perception that plastic contamination represents a long-term hazard to soil health and agroecosystem sustainability.

In this context, biodegradable and bio-based plastics, collectively

referred to as bioplastics, have gained attention as an alternative to conventional polymers. Their use is expected to increase markedly in the coming years, driven by regulatory pressure and the demand for environmentally compatible materials [12, 13]. Bioplastics are commonly marketed as materials that degrade after use, thereby reducing long-term accumulation in soils. However, their environmental performance under realistic agricultural conditions remains insufficiently constrained, particularly regarding the completeness of degradation, the formation of intermediate residues, and the long-term ecological consequences.

1.2. Why “biodegradable” does not necessarily mean environmentally safe

The term ‘biodegradable’ is commonly interpreted as synonymous with environmental safety. In the context of agricultural soils, this assumption has led to the widespread perception that bioplastics represent a presumed environmentally safer alternative to conventional polymers. However, biodegradability is not an intrinsic property of the material, but rather a process-dependent outcome that varies depending on polymer chemistry, physical characteristics, environmental conditions, and time scale [12].

In soil environments, polymer transformation encompasses a continuum of processes ranging from physical disintegration and surface erosion to chemical depolymerization, microbial assimilation, and variable degrees of mineralization, depending on environmental conditions, into CO_2 , water, or methane under aerobic and anaerobic conditions, respectively [14]. Many studies describe material “degradation” based on weight loss, fragmentation, or surface alterations, despite these metrics providing limited information on the fate of polymer-derived carbon. As a result, fragmentation and true biodegradation are frequently conflated, obscuring the distinction between temporary size reduction and permanent environmental removal [15].

This ambiguity is particularly relevant in agricultural soils, where repeated plastic inputs, seasonal variability, and complex microbial networks can promote incomplete degradation and accumulation of intermediate residues, including biodegradable microplastics (bio-MP). These particles may persist long enough to interact with soil biota, alter microbial community structure, or influence nutrient cycling before complete mineralization occurs [16]. From a hazard-oriented perspective, these transient but recurrent exposures warrant careful assessment, especially in long-term, large-scale agricultural deployment scenarios.

Importantly, the environmental behavior of bioplastics is highly heterogeneous. While some polymers exhibit slow or incomplete degradation under ambient soil conditions, others, particularly microbially synthesized polyesters, have demonstrated a higher propensity for microbial assimilation across diverse environments [16]. This variability highlights the need to move beyond generalized claims of

biodegradability toward a more nuanced, evidence-based assessment of polymer fate and associated soil hazards.

In recent years, several reviews have addressed specific aspects of the environmental behavior of bioplastics in soil systems (Table 1). Some studies have synthesized the impact of plastic particles on soil properties and the soil microbial, providing evidence of the physical, chemical, and microbial alterations associated with their presence.

Other studies have focused on the use of bioplastics in agriculture, describing their degradation processes in soil and the emerging challenges related to the formation of microplastics, as well as their potential ecotoxicological impact resulting from their degradation. Furthermore, more general reviews have been published comparing fossil-based and bioplastics in terms of sustainability, substitution, potential, or analyzing definitions and evaluation methods for biodegradable materials.

However, most of these studies address biodegradation in isolation, without linking analytical methodologies to the associated biological responses. Therefore, the environmental fate of carbon from bioplastics is not evaluated and integrated, nor are the implications of this evidence for risk assessment in real agricultural soils.

For this purpose, this review takes a bibliometrics-based, hazard-focused approach to critically synthesize the current knowledge on bioplastics in agricultural soils. It integrates available evidence on: (i) bioplastic transformation pathways and environmental fate in soil systems, with explicit distinction between physical disintegration and true biodegradation; (ii) impacts on soil microbial communities and soil functionality under laboratory and field conditions; and (iii) the analytical techniques used to detect, identify, and quantify bioplastics in

soil matrices, with emphasis on their suitability and limitations for environmental hazard assessment.

In doing so, this review goes beyond descriptive synthesis by identifying critical knowledge gaps related to carbon mass balance, methodological biases in degradation studies, biomicroplastics formation and persistence, and the limited transferability of laboratory results to realistic agricultural conditions. This work aims to provide a more robust framework for evaluating the environmental performance and potential risks of bioplastics in agrarian soils.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Bibliometric search

Data collection was conducted using the Web of Science database and included articles published between 2020 and 2025. We implemented quantitative methods to analyse the selected keywords ("bioplastic*" OR "biodegradable plastic*" OR "polylactic acid" OR "PLA" OR "polyhydroxyalkanoate*" OR "PHA" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate" OR "PHB" OR "poly (3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)" OR "PHBV" OR "polybutylene succinate" OR "PBS"), combined with degradation-related terms ("biodegradation" OR "degradation") and environmental context terms ("soil" OR "agriculture*").

The search, focused on environmental and ecological impacts, yielded 92 documents and was refined by adding the following keywords: "microbiome" OR "microbial diversity" OR "soil fertility" OR "nutrient cycling" OR "plant growth" OR "activity assay" OR "toxicity" OR

Table 1

Comparative summary of the scope of review studies on bioplastic degradation, impact on biological systems, and analytical techniques. A check mark indicates the thematic areas covered by each review.

Title	Scope	Degradation process	Open-field study presence	Carbon fate	Analytical challenges	Biological impact	Cite
The Interaction of Microplastics and Microbioplastics with Soil and a Comparison of Their Potential to Spread Pathogens	Summarizes the impact of plastic particles on soil properties and the soil microbial community.					✓	[17]
Embracing Nature's Clockwork: Crafting Plastics for Degradation in Plant Agricultural Systems	Synthesizes recent advances in agricultural bioplastics, soil degradation processes, and microplastic challenges.	✓				✓	[18]
Degradation of biodegradable plastics in waste management systems and the open environment: A critical review	Identifies limited data on microplastic generation and release during plastic degradation.	✓	✓	✓			[19]
A Review on Biodegradation of Bioplastics in Different Environmental Conditions	Highlights the role of bioplastics in environmental sustainability and fungal biodegradation.	✓					[20]
Ecotoxicological Impact of Bioplastics Biodegradation: A Comprehensive Review	Provides a comprehensive overview of bioplastic biodegradation and its ecotoxicological impacts.	✓				✓	[21]
A critical review of biodegradable plastic mulch films in agriculture: Definitions, scientific background and potential impacts	Examines bioplastic degradation, microplastic formation, and interactions with soil systems.	✓	✓	✓		✓	[22]
A Review of Biodegradable Plastics: Chemistry, Applications, Properties, and Future Research Needs	Reviews biodegradable plastics, including definitions, evaluation methods, and industrial applications.	✓	✓		✓		[1]
Are bioplastics an ecofriendly alternative to fossil fuel plastics?	Compares fossil-based plastics and bioplastics in terms of substitution potential, life cycle, and environmental impacts.	✓		✓		✓	[23]
Research progress on degradation of biodegradable micro-nano plastics and its toxic effect mechanism on soil ecosystem.	Analyzes degradation and toxicity mechanisms of bioplastic nanoparticles in soil ecosystems.	✓				✓	[24]
This revision	Critically synthesizes current knowledge on bioplastics in agricultural soils, focusing on their degradation pathways, impacts on soil microbial functions, and analytical methods, while identifying key knowledge gaps and limitations for environmental risk assessment.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

"inoculation". A second search, aimed at identifying analytical tools for biodegradation assessment, resulted in 93 documents following the addition of: "identification" OR "detection" OR "chromatography" OR "FTIR" OR "Raman" OR "GC-MS" OR "TGA" OR "SEM" OR "thermal analysis" OR "pyrolysis" OR "LC-MS".

Studies on aquatic environments were excluded by filtering for terms such as "marine", "seawater", "ocean", "sea", "coastal", or "estuarine". In addition, research focused on industrial processes was discarded by excluding the keywords "bioconversion", "production", "synthesis", "plasticizer", "thermal properties", "mechanical properties", and "dynamic characteristics". Finally, studies addressing chemical pollution were removed by excluding "pesticide", "herbicide", "fungicide", "insecticide", "organic pollutant*", and "contaminant*", thereby ensuring the dataset remained specific to biodegradable polymer-related topics.

To identify relevant thematic areas without compromising dataset richness, a minimum threshold of three co-occurrences was established, allowing for the inclusion of both highly representative terms and less frequent but potentially emerging topics in the research field. Data normalization was performed using the *association strength* method.

3. Bioplastics used in agricultural soils

3.1. Definition, classification, and agricultural relevance of bioplastics

The term "bioplastic" encompasses a heterogeneous group of polymeric materials that differ in terms of raw material origin, chemical structure, and environmental behavior [25]. In the agricultural context, this heterogeneity is particularly relevant, as materials classified under the same label may have very different degradation pathways and persistence in the soil [12].

Bioplastics are commonly classified by the origin of the raw material (bio-based versus fossil-based) and by biodegradability; however, these criteria are not equivalent and should not be used interchangeably. Bio-based plastics may be non-biodegradable, while biodegradable polymers may be entirely fossil-derived [26]. Consequently, classification based on origin provides a limited view of environmental fate in soils, where degradation depends on polymer chemistry, physical form, soil properties, and duration of exposure, with origin being less relevant in this context.

3.2. Main bioplastic polymers used in agriculture and their soil exposure pathways

The use of plastics in the agricultural sector has expanded considerably due to their ability to improve crop yields and optimize resource use. Conventional plastics are widely used in mulch films, irrigation systems, greenhouse covers [27], plant pots, and controlled-release systems [28]. Among these applications, mulch films represent the predominant use, as they effectively suppress weeds, reduce water evaporation, regulate soil temperature, and improve nutrient use efficiency [8]. However, the excessive use of non-biodegradable polymers, such as low-density polyethylene (LDPE), poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC), and ethylene copolymers, has led to a progressive accumulation of plastic waste in agricultural soils. These materials not only have limited recyclability but also require post-harvest removal. In many cases, their accumulation in landfills or illegal burning results in significant labour and infrastructure costs, thereby further exacerbating their negative environmental effects [29].

In this context, bioplastics are emerging as an alternative to conventional plastics used in agriculture, intending to maintain agronomic benefits while reducing environmental persistence [23]. Their use in agriculture is mainly focused on biodegradable mulch films, but also extends to encapsulation systems for agrochemicals, seed coatings, nursery pots, and greenhouse materials designed for controlled degradation after use. A wide variety of bioplastics are currently available for

agricultural use (Table 2); among those derived from natural polysaccharides, starch-based bioplastics are the most prominent. Starch is a renewable resource widely used due to its ease of processing and microbial degradability. However, it presents drawbacks, including low moisture resistance and incompatibility with hydrophobic polymers [30]. (Figs. 1-2)

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA), obtained through the controlled fermentation of sugars by specific microorganisms, is widely used in agriculture due to its commercial availability and favourable mechanical properties. It is characterized as comparable to polystyrene [31]. However, numerous studies have shown that PLA exhibits limited degradation under environmental conditions, requiring high temperatures to achieve significant degradation [32].

Poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT), an aliphatic-aromatic copolyester, is predominantly fossil-derived and consists of both aliphatic segments and aromatic terephthalate units. It stands out for its excellent flexibility and high biodegradability under environmental conditions, making it a key component in commercial formulations for agricultural mulching films [33]. Other aliphatic polyesters, such as poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) is also a viable alternative to non-biodegradable plastics, as it shows good thermal stability and flexibility, although their rigidity often requires blending with other polymers to optimize their performance [34].

Microbial-synthesized polyesters, including polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), constitute a distinct class of bioplastics characterized by their biological origin [35]. These polymers are produced and metabolized by microorganisms as they are a carbon reserve polymer, and their degradation in soil has been described through well-established enzymatic pathways, suggesting a closer relationship between polymer degradation and microbial metabolism than with other chemically synthesized polyesters. The most widely studied PHAs are polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) and its copolymer polyhydroxyvalerate (PHBV), both of which exhibit barrier properties comparable to those of conventional polymers and have high degradation rates [35, 36].

These materials can be blended with other polymers to enhance specific properties. For example, incorporating cellulose into PLA/PHB blends accelerates decomposition [37]. To make these materials more suitable for agricultural applications, various additives such as titanium dioxide (TiO₂) have been incorporated to improve specific properties, including biodegradability, mechanical strength, crystallinity, and rheological behavior, thereby expanding their range of potential applications [38]. Nevertheless, the use of such additives requires rigorous evaluation, as they may be released into the environment through leaching or during degradation, potentially generating toxic effects on soil and crops [39]. Several bioplastics are already commercially available for agricultural use. In the case of mulching films, *Mater-Bi*® and *Ecovio*® are two biodegradable options based mainly on starch and PLA, respectively [40].

According to the literature, PLA is the most extensively studied bioplastic, followed by PBAT, various plant-derived polymers, and PHAs (Fig. 3a). Among the plant-based polymers (excluding starch and cellulose due to their prominence as bioplastics), hemp, jute, and wheat stand out. In the case of blends (Figure S1), the most frequent are PLA/PBAT and PBAT/PLA. Within the PHA family, PHB is the most studied, followed by PHBV. Other materials, such as polyurethane (PU), PHS, and PVA, appear less frequently, indicating a bias toward commercially available polymers, which could delay the identification of more sustainable alternatives in specific contexts. Experiments involving bioplastic-origin films constitute most studies (Fig. 3b), consistent with the widespread use of mulching in agriculture. The second most studied bioplastic form is microplastics (MPs), reflecting increasing concern about the persistence of plastic fragments in agricultural soils. Notably, nearly 25% of the reviewed studies did not specify the physical form of the bioplastic under evaluation, seriously limiting the ability to reach objective conclusions, since geometry directly influences degradation rates and hinders comparability across studies.

Table 2

Properties of the most commercialized bioplastics and their agricultural uses.

Origin	Bioplastic	Monomers	Advantages	Disadvantages	Uses in agriculture	Cite
<i>Plant origin</i>	Starch	Glucose	Biodegradable, resistant, flexible, non-toxic, transparent	Low moisture resistance, low barrier properties	Mulching films, packaging	[30]
<i>Chemical synthesis</i>	Poly(lactic acid) (PLA)	Lactic acid	Biodegradable under industrial conditions, biocompatible, non-toxic, good processability, transparent	High fragility, low barrier properties, and low degradation rate under environmental conditions	Mulching films, irrigation pipes, and packaging	[1, 41]
	Polybutylene terephthalate adipate (PBAT)	Adipic acid, terephthalic acid, and 1,4-butanediol	Biodegradable, excellent film-forming ability, high flexibility, and good mechanical properties	-	Mulching films, bags, coatings	[42]
<i>Synthesized by microorganisms</i>						
	Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs)		Biodegradable, biocompatible, high barrier properties, structural versatility	Low thermal stability, brittleness, and difficult processing	Mulching films, coating of bioactive products, and packaging, high prices	[1, 43]
1.	Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB)	Hydroxybutyrate	Biodegradable in many environments	High crystallinity and brittleness	Those typical of PHAs	[44]
2.	Polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate (PHBV)	Hydroxybutyrate + hydroxyvalerate	The addition of 3-hydroxyvalerate increases the hardness and flexibility of the polymer	-	Those typical of PHAs	[44]

Fig. 1. Co-occurrence network of key terms associated with bioplastics in soil.

CLASSIFICATION OF BIOPLASTICS

Fig. 2. Classification of bioplastics according to their origin and biodegradability.

Fig. 3. (a) Types of bioplastics analyzed in the reviewed studies; (b) Physical formats of bioplastics used in degradation experiments.

3.3. Bioplastics degradation in soil

Bioplastics undergo different physical and chemical transformations once they reach the environment. In agricultural soils, bioplastics are exposed to fluctuations in temperature, humidity, and microbial activity, conditions that can lead to partial degradation and fragmentation rather than complete mineralization of the polymer. To understand this process, it is important to differentiate between *disintegration*, *degradation*, and *biodegradation*.

Disintegration refers to the breakdown of the polymer into smaller fragments without chemical alteration, which can be assessed through parameters such as weight or surface loss. *Degradation*, on the other hand, corresponds to the irreversible alteration of the material due to the breaking of molecular chains, which changes its original properties. For this breakdown to occur, environmental conditions, such as temperature, humidity, sunlight exposure (abiotic factors), and, above all, the presence of living organisms (biotic factors), are key [45]. Therefore, *biodegradation* occurs through the action of microorganisms, such as bacteria and fungi, which, with depolymerizing enzymes, decompose polymers into oligomers, dimers, or monomers that can be incorporated into their metabolism as a source of carbon and energy. It can be totally finalized when the polymers are mineralized, that is, being transformed to carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water (H₂O), producing heat under aerobic conditions, or methane (CH₄) and CO₂ under anaerobic conditions [14]. The efficiency of this process can be determined by measuring gases such as CO₂, O₂, or CH₄ [46, 47].

The biodegradation process includes the following stages (Fig. 4): (1) colonization, during which microorganisms adhere to the surface of the material, and forming biofilms; (2) biodeterioration, where enzymes or other degrading agents attack the material, creating pores that increase the available surface for adhesion; (3) metabolism and depolymerization, during which the chemical bonds that make up the polymer break down, producing simpler molecules; (4) assimilation, in which these products are incorporated into microbial metabolism, and finally, (5) mineralization occurs, referring to the production of energy, cellular biomass, and stable end products [36]. However, the biodegradability of a polymer depends on multiple factors, including intrinsic properties (such as thickness, water affinity, molecular mass, and crystalline structure) and environmental conditions. Therefore, a biodegradable plastic may or may not degrade depending on its surroundings and the time elapsed [48].

3.4. Characteristics of bioplastics related to their degradation

The susceptibility of a polymer to degradation depends directly on its physical and chemical properties, ranging from its molecular structure (functional groups, molecular weight) to higher-order structures such as crystallinity and surface morphology. These parameters are closely linked to the rate and efficiency of degradation [46, 49, 50]. Barros et al. (2023) observed that PLA with a higher molecular weight (10,000 g mol⁻¹ vs. 4000 g mol⁻¹) exhibited a lower degradation rate, since longer polymer chains are less susceptible to enzymatic assimilation [51].

Fig. 4. Plastic biodegradation process.

Another critical factor is the glass transition temperature (T_g), the thermal threshold above which amorphous regions of the polymer gain flexibility, facilitating access to water or chemicals. For PLA, this glass transition temperature is 58 °C, which limits its degradation at ambient temperature [32].

Highly crystalline structures hinder water penetration and thus hydrolysis rates [52–54]. However, degradation can be self-reinforcing, as

crystallinity often decreases during degradation, facilitating further breakdown. In contrast, for PBS, degradation increases crystallinity, possibly because amorphous regions degrade first or because the test conditions exceed the T_g , inducing new crystallization [55]. Regarding thickness, since polymer erosion and hydrolysis primarily occur at the surface, greater thickness reduces degradation. Burial studies of PHBV after 5 months in soil have shown that fragments with a thickness of

Fig. 5. (a) Thickness of the analyzed bioplastic films. (b) Proportion of studies conducted under field conditions versus laboratory conditions. (c) Biodegradation environments reported in the literature: buried soil, surface soil, and liquid culture media.

0.5 mm exhibit 25% greater degradation than those with a thickness of 2 mm [41]. Analysis of the thickness of bioplastics reported in the reviewed literature (Fig. 5a) indicates that films generally present thicknesses below 1 mm. Notably, a significant number of publications (26 articles, data not shown) fail to report the thickness of the bioplastic under study. This omission is a critical point to note, as thickness is a key factor in understanding degradation rates.

Moreover, a larger surface area in plastic samples may accelerate degradation by exposing more binding sites to enzymatic action [55]. Surface characteristics are equally crucial: rough or porous surfaces, or those with low hydrophobicity and tenacity, enhance wettability and microbial penetration, thereby promoting degradation [46, 56]. These properties can be modified using blends, fillers, or additives. Their application is highly versatile and depends on the desired material characteristics [44]. Functional fillers such as carbonates or organic salts like CaCO_3 can increase crystallinity, thereby enhancing the degradation rate [57]. Furthermore, polymers with reduced water affinity can be obtained through hydrophobic coatings using waxes or by blending with more hydrophobic polymers, such as PLA mixed with lignocellulosic residues [58–60].

3.5. The influence of abiotic factors on bioplastic degradation

Environmental factors play a fundamental role in the degradation of bioplastics, as previously mentioned. The most relevant factors are temperature and moisture, as they directly influence physicochemical and biological reactions. Temperature has been shown to accelerate the degradation rate significantly [61]. Dissanayake et al. (2024) reported a 6.1% degradation of PLA at 58°C, compared to only 1.7% at 25°C after 33 weeks, due to the hydrolysis of ester bonds above 30°C [32].

Humidity is a key parameter for degradation processes, as water availability regulates hydrolytic reactions and microbial metabolism; however, its effects are not linear and depend on the specific context. Zhang et al. (2022) clearly illustrate this effect in PLA/PBAT films, reporting a mass loss of $60.16 \pm 5.86\%$ at 60% relative humidity, compared with substantially lower values of $15.84 \pm 0.35\%$ and $10.37 \pm 0.92\%$ at 90% and 30% humidity, respectively, with statistically significant differences among treatments [62].

pH also directly affects microbial activity by influencing the structure and functionality of enzymes involved in material degradation. PBAT-degrading bacteria exhibit optimal enzymatic activity at specific pH values, such as pH 7 for *Roseibium aggregatum* ZY-1 [63], whereas *Lactobacillus paracasei* T1–9 showed higher activity at pH 6 [64].

Another critical factor is UV radiation, particularly under outdoor conditions. UV exposure induces photodegradation of the bioplastic surface, facilitating subsequent microbial degradation. This approach is employed as a pre-treatment strategy for bioplastic degradation [65]. However, in non-photostabilized PBAT films, UV treatment has been observed to reduce solubility and enzymatic hydrolysis capacity due to the formation of cross-links in the molecular structure, thereby decreasing the degradation rate [66].

Carbon content in soil is also a relevant factor. Villena et al. (2022) found that higher soil carbon content was associated with increased degradation rates of commercial mulch films, with a degradation order of starch > PLA > polyethylene (PE) [40]. According to Baldera-Moreno et al. (2024), an initial C/N ratio of 30–40 yielded the highest PLA degradation rates. However, in the absence of oxygen (i.e., without turning), PLA did not fully degrade after 180 days, despite an optimal C/N ratio [41]. Similarly, Wang et al. (2024) observed that under aerobic conditions, PHB and PHBV reached degradation rates of $83.9 \pm 1.3\%$ and $81.2 \pm 1.7\%$, respectively, after 77 days, whereas 117 days were required to achieve similar rates under anaerobic conditions [14].

Despite the importance of these factors, in the reviewed articles only ambient temperature was reported in 53.38% of the reviewed literature, followed by pH (38.98%) and soil moisture (24.57%), among other factors (Fig. 6). This lack of information introduces substantial

Fig. 6. Environmental and soil-related variables associated with bioplastic degradation.

experimental variability, hindering the identification of key determinants in bioplastic degradation and limiting the comparability across studies. All these factors are, to some extent, integrated into seasonality, latitude, and the degradation rate (Table 3). According to Rumi et al. (2024), the degradation of cellulose films buried in soil required 63 days for complete decomposition at the end of summer, whereas in spring, 112 days were needed [67]. Similarly, Chien et al. (2022) reported lower PBSA degradation activity in winter than in summer [68].

3.6. The influence of biotic factors on bioplastic degradation

Microbial presence, community composition, and functional capacity play a key role in shaping degradation outcomes. The accumulation of plastic waste in natural environments has led to the adaptation of diverse bacterial and fungal communities capable of producing esterases, lipases, or depolymerases that can use these polymers as carbon and energy sources. In this context, metagenomic exploration of such environments holds excellent potential for identifying microorganisms and genes involved in plastic degradation [76, 77].

Numerous bacterial and fungal species have been reported to have biodegradation capabilities [68, 78–80]. These microorganisms primarily act through depolymerization processes, breaking down the polymer's crystalline structure to release oligomers and monomers, which are subsequently assimilated into their metabolism (Table 4). For instance, *Bacillus infantis* can degrade PHB [81], and *Pseudomonas sichuanensis* [82] and *Trichoderma* spp. [83] can use PBAT as their sole carbon source.

In the case of PHAs, the PHB degradation pathway involves the hydrolysis of PHB into 3-hydroxybutyrate monomers by PHB depolymerase (PhaZ), followed by the conversion of 3-hydroxybutyrate into acetoacetate by 3-hydroxybutyrate dehydrogenase (BdhA), which can be further assimilated into central cellular metabolic pathways. These key enzymes are encoded by the phaZ and bdhA genes, respectively [75]. Similarly, the strain BA1S of *Purpureocillium lilacinum*, isolated from agricultural soils, demonstrated a remarkable ability to degrade PBAT plastic films. Its lipolytic enzyme activities were induced during coculture with PBAT, and the cutinase gene was significantly upregulated during PBAT degradation, highlighting its enzymatic contribution to polymer breakdown [72]. Additionally, *Bacillus safensis* PLA1006 was found to produce proteases and esterases, with proteases likely playing the primary role in the biodegradation of PLA [22].

As a result, the targeted addition of microorganisms or microbial consortia to accelerate bioplastic degradation (bioaugmentation) has gained attention. Examples include the use of landfill leachates or

Table 3

Open-field degradation studies. Values marked with “-” indicate that this data was not reported in the study.

Bioplastic	Location	Buried or surface	Temperature (°C)		Humidity (%)		Duration (Months)	Calendar period	Weight loss	Cite	
			Ambient	Soil	Ambient	Soil					
Cellulose	USA (33.56°N)	Buried	-	-	-	-	12 ± 2	Study 1: ~2 Study 2: ~3	Study 1: May - June Study 2: August - October	100 % after 63 days in late summer and 112 days in spring	[67]
Starch	Lithuania (54.90°N)	Buried	26.3	24.3	-	-	~6	~6	June - November	100%	[69]
PLA/RF (Cellulose)	China (38.89°N)	Buried	-	-	-	-	12	-	-	PLA/RF10 – 12.01%, PLA/RF20 – 14.17% PLA/RF30 – 19.92%	[70]
Jute/Jute/PLA (80:20)	Croatia (45.53°N)	Surface	13.9	-	93.8	-	~11	~11	April – February	After 8 months: Jute 100 %; Hemp 100 %; PLA blends ~20–30 %;	[71]
Hemp/Hemp/PLA (80:20)PLA	Croatia (45.53°N)	Surface	-	-	-	-	~11	~11	April – February	Pure PLA ~0 %	[72]
PLA	Germany (51.12°N)	Buried	6–7.5	-	-	-	~13	~13	November – December (following year)	Increase in thickness (0.2–0.4 mm) and decrease in air permeability 33.9 ± 1.8	[73]
PBSA	Algeria (28.03°N)	Buried	-	-	-	-	12	12	-	PLA: ~60% PLA/PC (90:10): ~70% PLA/PC (70:30): ~80% PLA/PC (50:50): ~90%	[74]
PLA/PC	Germany (51.12°N)	Buried	8.9–9.7	-	-	-	~10	~10	-	70%	[75]

Table 4

Bioplastic-degrading microorganisms.

Bioplastic	Microorganism involved	Source	Degradation efficiency	Cite
PBAT	<i>Azotobacter vinelandii</i>	Compost	12.12% after 40 days	[85]
	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i> T1–9	Liquid culture	1.77 ± 0.08 % after 14 days	[64]
	<i>Pseudomas sichuanensis</i> L3	Liquid culture	6.2 ± 0.23 % after 30 days	[82]
	<i>Trichoderma</i> KKP 534	Liquid culture	0.043% after 9 days	[83]
	Consortium of <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> , <i>Bacillus cereus</i> , and <i>Bacillus paramycoides</i>	Liquid culture	26.1% after 6 days	[86]
PLA	Microbial consortium (<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i> , <i>Serratia marcescens</i> , <i>Cladosporium sphaerospermum</i> , and <i>Rhodotorula mucilaginosa</i>)	Liquid culture	The time required to reach 90% degradation of PLA films was reduced by almost 27%	[87]
	<i>Bacillus toyonensis</i> and <i>Bacillus albus</i>	Compost	Significant increase in bacterial respiration rate	[88]
	<i>Bacillus safensis</i>	Liquid culture	8% after 30 days	[31]
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Soil	1.20 ± 0.03% after 180 days	[89]
	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Soil	3.42 ± 0.06% after 180 days	[89]
PHB	<i>Aeromonas caviae</i> Kuk1-(34)	Liquid culture	89% after 49 days	[79]
	<i>Aeromonas caviae</i> Kuk1-(34)	Soil	71% after 49 days	[79]
	<i>Bacillus infantis</i> PD3	Liquid culture	98.71% after 5 days	[81]
PBSA	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> cepa L30	Liquid culture	30.2% after 30 days	[68]
	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i> cepa HC	Liquid culture	47.5% after 30 days	[68]
	<i>Aspergillus oryzae</i> RIB40	Liquid culture	27.5% after 30 days	[68]
	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i> cepa HC	Soil	78% after 30 days	[68]

vermicompost to enhance PLA [84] and cassava starch [15]. Recently, the use of insects such as mealworms (*Tenebrio molitor*) has also been explored for plastic decomposition by harnessing their gut microbiome [39].

Overall, these examples demonstrate that degradation rates reported for bioplastics in soil are strongly influenced by numerous parameters such as temperature, moisture, and microbial community context. Such context dependency highlights the importance of the experimental setting. In the reviewed literature, most experiments are conducted under controlled laboratory conditions (83%) as opposed to open-field environments (17%) (Fig. 5b). While laboratory settings offer significant advantages, such as variable control and process isolation, they fail to capture the complexity of real-world environments, where environmental fluctuations play a decisive role in the degradation process. Consequently, the field studies are particularly valuable, although insufficient to establish generalizable patterns.

Degradation assessments are primarily performed in soil (65%), with burial tests being the predominant method, aiming to simulate the final disposal conditions of bioplastics (Fig. 5c). Other studies, such as those conducted in culture media, represent a smaller proportion (14.17%). They are mainly focused on the controlled characterization of depolymerizing enzymes or the identification of novel degrading microorganisms. A limited number of investigations address degradation on the soil surface (7%), which is especially useful for evaluating the suitability of bioplastics for agricultural applications. The remaining studies evaluate degradation by incorporating bioplastics directly into the soil matrix.

It is important to note that the favourable degradation observed under controlled laboratory conditions may not translate into effective mineralization in agricultural fields. Without explicit consideration of these factors and their temporal variability, data on degradation may overestimate environmental dissipation and underestimate the potential accumulation of polymer-derived waste after repeated application cycles.

4. Research landscape and structural biases in bioplastic-soil studies

Co-occurrence network analysis (Fig. 1) shows that research on bioplastics in agricultural soils is dominated mainly by the study of their

degradation, with central keywords such as “degradation” and “biodegradation”. These terms are closely related to “soil,” “PLA,” and its variants (“PLA,” “polylactic acid,” “poly lactide”), as well as ‘films’ and “blends,” indicating a strong predominance of PLA-based materials used in agricultural applications.

Keywords related to microplastic pollution (“microplastics”, “microplastic”, “microplastic pollution”) form a distinct yet interconnected cluster, reflecting the increasing integration of bioplastics into the broader discussion on soil microplastics. However, despite the relatively high frequency of these terms, concepts directly related to the long-term fate, such as carbon tracking, accumulation, or mineralization, appear less frequently and have weaker connections, indicating that the fate of polymer-derived carbon remains a secondary concern.

Specific terms related to soil exposure, such as “soil burial,” “agriculture,” and “plant growth,” are present but occupy peripheral positions in the network. This could indicate that agricultural soils are often treated primarily as experimental matrices rather than as dynamic systems governing degradation pathways, biological interactions, and cumulative exposure.

Keyword co-occurrence analysis reveals structural biases that limit an environmental risk-oriented interpretation: research focuses mainly on PLA, while other biodegradable polymers are underrepresented, making it difficult to extrapolate degradation behaviors. Degradation is primarily addressed by focusing on material study, with little connection to concepts such as carbon fate and long-term persistence, and biological impact indicators appear weakly linked to degradation metrics.

It should be noted that microbially synthesized polyesters, including “polyhydroxyalkanoates,” “poly(3-hydroxybutyrate),” “PHB,” and “PHA bioplastics,” appear less frequently but with a relatively constant relationship to keywords related to microbial activity, biodegradation, and biopolymers. Although they are underrepresented compared to PLA, their position in the network suggests a closer conceptual association with microbial processes relevant to edaphic environments.

Overall, the co-occurrence network shows that current research prioritizes degradation performance and material behavior under controlled conditions, offering limited insight into long-term persistence, intermediate residues, and cumulative soil exposure, highlighting the need for integrated, polymer-specific, and environmentally relevant approaches to adequately assess risks in agricultural systems. The results of the analysis are summarized in Table S1.

5. Analytical platform to assess bioplastic degradation

Although bioplastics are commonly regarded as intrinsically safer due to their designed biodegradability, degradation in soil may be incomplete, resulting in fragmentation rather than full mineralization and the formation of biodegradable microplastics (bio-MPs) [90]. These intermediates may exhibit distinct environmental behavior compared to conventional microplastics due to their transient nature and the release of degradation by-products [91].

The treatment of soil samples for microplastic analysis presents specific challenges. The literature contains established extraction and purification protocols developed for chemically inert polymers. bio-MPs, on the other hand, are more susceptible to hydrolysis, which increases the risk of artificial degradation during sample pretreatment. Therefore, not all methods developed for assessing conventional MPs in soil are suitable for bio-MPs [92].

Commonly used steps, such as oxidative digestion and high-temperature drying, can selectively damage or eliminate bio-MPs, which would lead to an underestimation of their abundance. These methodological limitations, combined with the lack of standardized protocols specific to bio-MPs, introduce significant uncertainty in the comparability between studies, limiting a robust assessment of their presence, persistence, and associated environmental hazard in edaphic systems. Consequently, reliable evaluation of bioplastic degradation in soil requires analytical approaches that preserve sample integrity and

Table 5
Methods for identifying and characterizing bioplastics.

Analytical technique	Bioplastic studied	Application	Advantages and limitations	Cite
<i>Microscopic Methods</i>				
SEM	PHB/PLA	Visualization of cracks on the polymer surface	High image quality, requires sample preparation, qualitative analysis	[15]
Stereoscopic microscope	PLA	Surface visualization	Lower resolution than SEM	[99]
<i>Spectroscopic methods</i>				
XRD	Starch/Argan	Visualization of changes in diffraction peaks related to the crystallinity index	Fast and reproducible technique. Qualitative analysis requires sample purification	[56]
RMN	PBAT/PLA	Provides detailed information on molecular structure and chemical composition	Requires large sample quantities and expensive equipment	[100]
RAMAN	PHA	Allows identification of functional groups and evaluation of structural changes during degradation	Qualitative, non-destructive analysis, signal can be masked	[101]
FT-IR	PLA/PBAT	The carbonyl index is calculated based on the intensity of the absorption bands as an indicator of degradation	Qualitative, non-destructive analysis, application limited to the sample surface	[102]
<i>Thermal methods</i>				
TGA	PHB	Visualization of changes in the thermal degradation profile associated with the state of degradation	Requires little sample, qualitative and quantitative analysis, destructive, gases produced can be identified by coupling with MS	[43]
Pyrolysis	PHBV	The pyrolyzer releases degradation products that are then visualized and quantified using GC-MS	Promising tool for quantifying bioplastics in different matrices, high sensitivity, destructive	[103]
DSC	PLA	Visualization of lower molecular weight molecules indicating partial degradation of the polymer	Identification of physical properties and thermal transition points (T _g , T _m , ΔH), destructive	[104]
<i>Chromatographic methods</i>				
LC-MS	PBAT	Visualization of degradation products	High sensitivity, limited to volatile compounds	[86]
GPC	PLA/PPC	Decrease in average molar mass detected	Provides molecular weight distribution, but does not allow identification of compounds	[105]
GC-MS	PLA	Visualization of degradation products	High sensitivity. Requires prior pyrolysis or extraction	[106]

(continued on next page)

Table 5 (continued)

Analytical technique	Bioplastic studied	Application	Advantages and limitations	Cite
<i>Other methods</i>				
Biological oxygen demand	PBAT	Allows evaluation of oxygen consumption associated with microbial degradation of bioplastics	Easy technique, indirect method, results dependent on test conditions	[107]
CO ₂ emission	PLA	Detection of CO ₂ emitted as an indicator of biodegradation	Standardized method, easy, results may not be reliable	[87]
Weight loss	PLA/PBAT	Change in polymer weight associated with degradation	Fast, simple, low cost, but inaccurate and may lead to measurement errors	[108]

allow differentiation between material transformation, fragmentation, and true biodegradation. The analytical methodologies used to determine the biodegradability of bioplastics are summarized in Table 5.

From a morphological perspective, microscopy provides valuable qualitative information about the condition of the polymer surface. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is widely used in the literature and is highly effective for directly visualizing erosion, cracking, and surface heterogeneity during degradation. However, its application is subject to considerable variability, as degradation does not occur uniformly across the polymer surface, and it is not possible to derive a quantitative measure of degradation from the images obtained [93].

Gravimetric mass loss measurements are among the most applied methods due to their simplicity and practicality [94, 95]. Nevertheless, according to Wolf et al. (2023), this technique is prone to errors and becomes less informative when fragments are small, as part of the sample may be lost [96]. Moreover, polymer mass loss does not guarantee microbial assimilation, as demonstrated by Erkul & Ucaroglu (2025) [15]. As a result, gravimetric approaches may overestimate degradation under conditions favouring fragmentation rather than mineralization and are poorly suited for comparing degradation efficiency across studies using different polymer geometries or exposure conditions.

Spectroscopic techniques, particularly Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and Raman spectroscopy, are widely employed to monitor chemical changes such as ester bond cleavage and functional group modification. Stegenta-Dabrowska et al. (2024) using FTIR observed ester bond cleavage and the formation of hydroxyl groups in PLA samples at 59°C, while no significant changes were detected at 38°C, suggesting that PLA degradation requires thermophilic conditions [45]. Radu et al. (2021), through X-ray diffraction (XRD), identified greater degradation in PLA/PHB samples exposed to high temperatures than in those stored at ambient temperature [37].

While these techniques provide valuable insights into physico-chemical transformations, they are largely surface-sensitive. Moreover, spectral changes may also arise from abiotic hydrolysis, oxidative weathering, or organic matter contamination, complicating attribution to biological processes [66, 97]. In addition, spectroscopic techniques are inherently limited by particle size, as their detection capability depends on the minimum spatial resolution achievable, which constrains their applicability for nano- and submicron-sized MPs.

Chromatographic techniques provide precise quantification of intermediate and final degradation products. Kanwal et al. (2024) studied PBAT degradation using liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (LC-MS), identifying terephthalic acid, 1,4-butanediol,

and adipic acid as its characteristic monomers [86]. Rusetskaya et al. (2024) assessed degradation efficiency by assuming a 1:1 stoichiometry (PBAT: TPA) and measuring TPA in the medium via LC-MS [83]. Additionally, gel permeation chromatography (GPC) confirmed a 5.69% reduction in molecular weight in PBAT/PLA films incubated with earthworms compared to controls without earthworms [98]. Unlike morphological or spectroscopic techniques, chromatographic approaches allow more direct comparison between studies, as degradation products can be quantified in absolute terms and related to polymer-specific stoichiometry, facilitating cross-study assessment of degradation efficiency.

Thermal analysis techniques are frequently used to infer degradation through changes in crystallinity, melting behavior, or thermal stability. These are destructive techniques, but they offer high sensitivity. Parolini et al. (2024), using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), reported a decrease in the melting peak from 173°C to 168°C in PLA samples exposed to earthworms [104]. Brtnicky et al. (2024), using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), indicated incomplete PHB degradation in soil after eight weeks [43].

Thermal analysis combined with mass spectrometry (MS) is a powerful tool for identifying associated degradation products, extensively documented in the literature [109–112]. Reay et al. (2025) used Py-GC-MS to determine PHBV concentrations in soil samples with a calibration range of 0.5 µg to 15 µg [103], which demonstrates its high analytical sensitivity. A major drawback of these analytical strategies is that their detection limits are expressed using different metrics: while spectroscopic techniques often report particle size, thermal and pyrolytic methods report minimum detectable mass or concentration. This discrepancy complicates direct comparison between analytical families, although thermal and pyrolytic methods still allow sensitive quantification of polymer residues at trace levels.

Respirometric approaches, including CO₂ evolution and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), are the only methods capable of directly assessing microbial mineralization and are therefore highly relevant for environmental risk evaluation. These systems are well-developed and described in international guidelines and standards [96]. Using cellulose as a reference material, Erkul et al. (2025) monitored PLA and PHB degradation over 180 days by capturing released CO₂ with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solutions [15]. However, it is important to note that biodegradation may be overestimated, as not all evolved CO₂ necessarily originates from the plastic. To address this, blanks without plastic could be included to account for background CO₂, and experiments can also be conducted in sterilized soil to determine the fraction of CO₂ specifically attributable to microbial activity [113].

Isotopic labelling of polymers provides unequivocal attribution of evolved CO₂ to polymer-derived carbon and enables carbon mass balance assessment but is rarely applied under realistic agricultural conditions [103, 114]. Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is another approach that evaluates oxygen consumption associated with the microbial degradation of bioplastics [107].

According to the reviewed literature, the current analytical toolbox used to evaluate bioplastic degradation in soil is dominated by methods that characterize material transformation rather than environmental fate (Fig. 7a). Other methods, including XPC, Py-GC/MS, and RAMAN, are less frequently represented despite their ability to provide detailed molecular insights into specific degradation mechanisms. Furthermore, most studies employ only one or two techniques (Fig. 7b).

Most studies rely on one or two accessible techniques, such as SEM, mass loss, or FTIR, which limits their ability to assess persistence, biodegradation, and carbon fate. This lack of methodological harmonization hampers direct comparison between studies, as different techniques target different degradation endpoints (surface alteration, mass loss, chemical transformation, or mineralization) and operate under distinct detection limits and selectivity constraints.

Relying on a single analytical technique generally provides an incomplete and potentially misleading picture of the degradation

Fig. 7. (a) Analytical techniques used to detect and quantify bioplastics in environmental matrices. (b) Relative contribution of each analytical technique in the reviewed studies.

process, as no individual method can fully capture all aspects of material transformation, fragmentation, and true biodegradation. However, integrating multiple analytical approaches increases complexity, enabling the establishment of polymer degradation and its links between structural changes occurring during degradation and the material’s behavior under real-world conditions. In the reviewed literature, studies employing diverse techniques assess degradation through morphological observation (microscopic techniques), changes in physicochemical properties (spectroscopic techniques), and the identification of degradation byproducts (thermal/chromatographic techniques).

Overall, given the complexity of polymer degradation, it is the integration of multiple analytical approaches that enables links to be established between structural changes occurring during degradation and the material’s behavior under real-world conditions. Combining morphological, spectroscopic, thermal, chromatographic, and respirometric methods enables a more robust linkage between structural transformation, degradation mechanisms, and environmental fate. Such detailed knowledge of how bioplastics transform in soil is crucial for assessing their subsequent effects on the soil–crop system, including

potential alterations to nutrient cycles, microbial communities, and crop performance.

6. Impact of bioplastics on the soil–crop agricultural system

Soil is the primary reservoir for agricultural plastic use [115]. The presence of bioplastics in soil goes beyond mere accumulation; it represents a biogeochemical alteration capable of reshaping nutrient cycles and bacterial communities [116–118]. Moreover, during degradation, bioplastics may release intermediate compounds [17] that affect the soil’s physicochemical parameters and functionality, alter the soil microbial community, impact crop performance, or induce toxicity in soil fauna (Fig. 8; Table 6). It is important to note that these biological responses must be interpreted according to the type of polymer, the level of exposure, and the stage of degradation.

6.1. Impact on crops

The agronomic applicability of bioplastics is fundamentally

Fig. 8. Conceptual overview of the impacts of bioplastics on the soil–plant system, emphasizing key hazard-relevant effects.

Table 6
Impact of bioplastics on crop, soil, and microbial community levels.

Bioplastic	Dose	Specie	Effects	Cite
<i>Effect on crop</i>				
PBAT	0.8 % w/w	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>)	Decrease in chlorophyll content, increased oxidative stress, and impaired plant growth	[119]
PHBV	0.06 – 3.2% w/w	Maize (<i>Zea mays</i> L.)	Reduced root and shoot biomass, lower height, and chlorophyll, C, N, and P content at higher PHBV doses; at low concentration (<0.06%), showed no significant effects	[103]
Starch	-	<i>Cucumis melo</i> L.	The use of biodegradable mulch films improved melon crop yields compared to conventional LDPE mulch films	[123]
PLA	0.2 % w/w	Oat and soybean	No significant effect on root traits, plant biomass, or ecosystem multifunctionality	[90]
PLA	0.1–5% w/w	Pak choi	Growth inhibition at 1% and 5% w/w;	[128]
PBAT/PLA	-	Eggplant, cherry tomato and pepper	Biodegradable PBAT/PLA films reduced the overall environmental impact	[124]
PBAT	0.05–2 % w/w	<i>Brassica chinensis</i> L. Chao1	High PBAT-MP concentrations significantly inhibited plant growth; a reduction in plant O ₂ content	[129]
PHB	1 % and 5 % w/w	Lettuce	Plant growth limitation	[127]
PLA	0.1–5 % w/w	Wheat	At high doses, inhibited growth, reduced shoot and root weight, and chlorophyll content	[14]
PLA/ PBAT/ PCC	-	Winter potatoes	Biodegradable films based on PBAT, PLA, and PPC reduce nutrient loss in the final stages of cultivation	[125]
PCL	0.02–0.2 – 2 % w/w	Rapeseed (<i>Brassica rapa</i> var. <i>oleifera</i> DC)	Decrease in soluble protein content	[130]
<i>Effect on biochemical soil parameters</i>				
PHBV	0.06–0.6–1.6 – 3.2% w/w	-	Greater hydrophobicity at high concentrations (1.6–3.2%) and higher NH ₄ ⁺ and NO ₃ ⁻ content because of the reduction of carbon mineralization, also producing a reduction of nitrogen use, mainly NH ₄ ⁺	[103]
PHB	5 g/L	-	Reduction in root biomass and enzymatic activities; effect mitigated by digestate application. Increase in dehydrogenase and urease activities, as	[43]

Table 6 (continued)

Bioplastic	Dose	Specie	Effects	Cite
			they serve as substrates for the soil microbial community, and a decrease in β-dehydrogenase activity, as their nature is mainly constituted by carbon bonds	
PBAT	-	-	After three years of continuous use of biodegradable films, the soil regained its functional balance	[131]
PLA	0.2% w/w	-	No significant effect on soil biochemical properties during one growing season (5 months)	[90]
PLA	0.1–1–5% w/w	-	Increase in MBN, DOC, and MBC, and reduction in pH and CEC	[128]
PBAT	0.05 % y 2 % p /p	-	Decrease in pH and increase in SOM, S-AKP, sDHA, SL, and S-CAT	[129]
PLA	0.1 %, 1 %, and 5 % w/w	-	At 1% and 5% w/w, caused pH decrease, DOC increase, and NO ₃ ⁻ reduction	[14]
PHB	1 %, and 5 % w/w	-	Increased carbon, nitrogen, sulfur, and phosphorus, as hydrophobicity, caused a nutrient mineralization inhibition	[127]
PLA	0.5 % and 1.5 % w/w	-	Increased pH and NH ₄ ⁺ , decreased NO ₃ ⁻ , reduced urease, sucrose, and alkaline phosphatase activities	[132]
<i>Effect on the soil microbial community</i>				
PBAT	-	-	Alteration of microbial communities by stimulating aerobic catabolic pathways and degradation of aromatic compounds	[133]
PBAT/PLA	-	-	Reduced alpha diversity and enrichment of taxa with degradative capacity	[134]
PLA	0.1 %, 1 %, and 5 % w/w	-	Increase in fermentative communities in flooded soils, leading to an opportunistic microbiome. Still, at 1–5% PLA-MP, a significant decrease in the richness, diversity, and evenness of the soil microbial community, resulting in a less abundant microbiome.	[135]
PLA	0.1 %, 1 %, and 5 % w/w	-	A decrease in richness, diversity, and evenness of the total soil microbial community is more exacerbated under anaerobic conditions	[136]

(continued on next page)

Table 6 (continued)

Bioplastic	Dose	Specie	Effects	Cite
PBAT/PLA	-	-	Increased rhizosphere microbial diversity, evidenced by higher Shannon and Chao1 indices and the enrichment of beneficial bacteria such as <i>Acidobacteria</i> and <i>Pseudomonas</i>	[137]
PHB	1 % and 5 % w/w	-	Reduced microbial diversity at high doses (1–5%)	[127]
PCL	0.02–0.2 – 2 % w/w	-	No effect on soil microbial community structure or diversity by the compromise between bioplastics and non-bioplastic specialists, which did not affect the final figure of diversity, but it changes the species	[130]
<i>Effect on soil microfauna</i>				
PBAT	2 and 6 % w/w	Earthworms (<i>Eisenia fétida</i>)	No effect on reproductive activity, but some genotoxicity was observed at high doses after 28 days	[119]
PLA	0.1% and 1% w/w	Earthworms (<i>Eisenia foetida</i>)	Modulation of oxidative status (increased superoxide dismutase and glutathione peroxidase activity); no tissue damage or behavioral alterations	[104]
PLA	0.1, 0.3, and 3 % w/w	Earthworms (<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>)	No adverse effects on mortality or weight change; PLA-MPs reduced Cd exposure in earthworms	[99]
PLA	1% w/w	<i>Eisenia nordenskioldi</i>	The presence of earthworms mitigated the impact of PLA on soil bacteria	[138]

MBN: Microbial Biomass Nitrogen; DOC: Dissolved Organic Carbon; MBC: Microbial Biomass Carbon; CIC: Cation Exchange Capacity; SOM: Soil Organic Matter; S-AKP: Soil Alkaline Phosphatase; sDHA: Soil Dehydrogenase Activity; SL: Soil Lipids; S-CAT: Soil Catalase Activity

conditioned by their ability to maintain crop productivity without compromising soil functionality. Although bioplastics are often regarded as inert replacements for conventional plastics, evidence suggests that their presence during cultivation actively influences soil nutrient dynamics and plant–soil interactions [119].

Crop responses to bioplastics are strongly polymer- and dose-dependent. According to Reay et al. (2025), maize (*Zea mays* L.) exposed to increasing concentrations of PHBV (0.06–3.2% w/w) exhibited reduced root and shoot biomass, lower plant height, and decreased chlorophyll, carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus content at higher concentrations (1.6% and 3.2%), while the lowest concentration (0.06%) showed no significant effects. Similar effects were observed in wheat, where only higher PLA concentrations (1% and 5%) inhibited growth, reduced shoot and root weight, and decreased chlorophyll content [14]. These effects are likely attributable to the increased microbial demand for carbon from the bioplastics, which can lead to nutrient immobilization and heightened competition between soil microbes and plants [43].

Likewise, PBAT at 0.8% w/w reduced chlorophyll content and increased oxidative stress markers [119], whereas more realistic exposures, such as those of oat (*Avena sativa* L.) and soybean (*Glycine max* (L.)

Merr.) to PLA films (0.2% w/w), did not significantly affect biomass or soil functionality [90]. Low doses of PBAT (0.05%) in *Brassica chinensis* and PHBV (0.06%) in maize showed no relevant physiological alterations [120, 121].

Moreover, degradation intermediates may directly affect crop toxicity. For instance, Liu et al. (2022) demonstrated that PBAT monomers (adipic acid, terephthalic acid, and 1,4-butanediol) caused greater phytotoxic effects than the polymer itself, with butanediol and terephthalic acid nearly completely inhibiting growth at a 1% concentration [122], highlighting that hazard assessments based solely on bulk polymer properties may underestimate risks associated with transient degradation products. In contrast, aqueous extracts from PHBV degradation, primarily composed of hydroxy acid monomers, were metabolically assimilable by soil microorganisms and plants, showing no detectable phytotoxicity in germination assays with garden cress (*Lepidium sativum*) [36], underscoring that “bioplastics” cannot be treated as a homogeneous category with respect to environmental safety.

Sellami et al. (2024) show that the use of commercial biodegradable mulch films improved melon crop yields by 23.4% compared to conventional LDPE mulch films [123]. Similarly, Xiong et al. (2024) indicate that PBAT mulch films used in solanaceous crops reduced the total environmental impact by 2.6%. This study indicates that much of the environmental burden associated with their use comes from the manufacturing stage [124]. Yang et al. (2023) point out that biodegradable films based on PBAT, PLA, and PPC allowed for better regulation of soil temperature and water levels than PE films, which reduced nutrient loss in later stages of cultivation [125].

In addition, various approaches seek to enhance the positive effects of these materials. To address nitrogen depletion, nitrogen-enriched PBS (N-PBS) composites with PLA were synthesized. This blend not only exhibited improved mechanical and thermal properties but also released nitrogenous degradation products that enhanced lettuce growth, chlorophyll content, soluble protein levels, and vitamin C [126]. Other approaches involve applying microbial consortia containing plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR), which support crop development and bioplastic biodegradation in soil [127].

6.2. Effects on soil

Bioplastics can alter soil during degradation, particularly through changes in nutrient mineralization and microbial dynamics. These alterations are mainly attributed to the so-called “priming effect,” which results from the introduction of an easily assimilable carbon source that stimulates microbial activity and temporarily limits nitrogen availability, thereby altering soil mineralization processes [139]. Reay et al. (2025) reported that adding PHBV to soil increased nitrogen and phosphorus demand, associated with nutrient immobilization by plastic-degrading microorganisms [103]. These findings align with those of Li et al. (2023), who observed that the presence of PBAT led to nitrogen limitation and inhibited nitrification processes [140]. In contrast, Han et al. (2024) indicated that PBAT promoted nitrogen fixation while reducing soil phosphorus content and enhancing carbon metabolism [121].

However, the increase in microbial activity resulting from the degradation of bioplastics can cause physicochemical changes in the soil. Liu et al. (2023) found that PLA degradation in soil was associated with soil acidification, the release of lactic acid monomers, and an increase in dissolved organic carbon, affecting nutrient availability [141]. It has been showed that PBAT and PLA film degradation over 33 weeks altered parameters such as pH, total carbon content, and electrical conductivity, [32] corroborated these results [32].

In the case of PHBV, its hydrophobicity reduces the bioavailability of compounds like ammonium and nitrate due to restricted mobility [103]. However, Chu et al. (2023) reported that PLA application to oat and soybean crops over five months did not affect soil biochemical properties or ecosystem multifunctionality [90]. This may be due to the high

temperatures required for PLA degradation and the short exposure time, as the effects were studied over a single crop cycle. For PBAT, a reduction in soil salinity was observed, attributed to decreased soil permeability caused by pore blockage [140]. Several studies have reported reduced aggregate stability and soil porosity, affecting water flow and aeration [91, 142].

While several long-term field studies indicate recovery of soil functionality after multi-year exposure [131], the limited number of such studies constrains extrapolation across agroecosystems, climates, and management practices. [131]. It is worth noting that the magnitude and direction of these effects may vary depending on the soil type, texture, organic matter content, or environmental conditions.

6.3. Effect on the soil microbial community

The presence of bioplastics in soil induces an alteration of the microbial populations in soil and its functionality as an additional carbon substrate, and through its ability to modify key physicochemical parameters of the soil, such as pH, nutrient availability, and redox conditions [103]. Microbial responses to bioplastics are highly polymer-specific and depend on degradation stage, exposure concentration, and environmental context.

For PHAs, which are naturally synthesized by bacteria as intracellular carbon and energy reserves [143] and related esterolytic enzymes, facilitating polymer depolymerization and microbial growth [81]. Bacterial groups, such as *Oxalobacteraceae* and *Shingomonadaceae*, were highly stimulated by PHB [127] and PHBV [103], as were saprophytic fungi, such as *Exophiala* and *Tetracladium*. In contrast, fungal genera such as *Gibellulopsis* and *Fusarium* declined significantly [103].

In the case of PBAT, its presence altered microbial communities by stimulating aerobic catabolic pathways and the degradation of aromatic compounds [144]. Bacterial genera, such as *Bacillus*, *Vicinamibacterales* [144], and *Pseudomonas* [145] known to produce esterases, lipases, and cutinase-like enzymes capable of hydrolyzing ester bonds in biodegradable plastics, were enriched in the presence of PBAT. While declines in *Shingomonas* and *Lyso bacter* suggest competitive displacement rather than uniform microbial stimulation [129].

Similarly, Li et al. (2024) found that PBAT/PLA exposure resulted in lower α -diversity, while enriching degradative taxa, such as *Nectriaceae* and *Pleosporeaceae* [146]. Nevertheless, Zhao et al. (2023) reported contrasting results, showing that PBAT/PLA mulch films significantly increased rhizosphere microbial diversity, as evidenced by higher Shannon and Chao1 indices and the enrichment of beneficial bacteria, such as *Acidobacteria* and *Pseudomonas* [137]. These communities fostered more complex and stable microbial networks, which are associated with enhanced soil resilience and more vigorous plant–microbe interactions, unlike the slight decline observed under PE treatments.

PLA degradation has been reported to drive significant physicochemical alterations in soil, notably promoting shifts in microbial communities through acidification processes. Wang et al. (2024) demonstrated that reduced pH resulting from PLA degradation favoured fermentative communities, such as *Clostridium* and *Sedimentibacter*, in flooded soils. At PLA-MP concentrations of 1%–5%, microbial richness, diversity, and evenness significantly declined, whereas PE-MP and 0.1% PLA-MP had a negligible impact [14].

Hao et al. (2024) evaluated the effects of various bioplastics on microbial communities, using PE as a control, showing that, compared to petroleum-derived materials (PBAT), PLA degradation products, such as starch monomers, exerted a strong preferential substrate utilization, resulting in greater microbial richness and diversity (PLA > PBAT > PE) [147], indicating that bioplastic-derived low-molecular-weight compounds may exert stronger ecological effects than non-degradable polymers [148].

At the functional level, several studies report increased activity of hydrolytic enzymes following bioplastic incorporation, reflecting microbial attempts to exploit new carbon sources [151]. However, such

increases are frequently followed by nutrient limitation, particularly nitrogen immobilization, which constrains mineralization and decouples enzymatic activity from effective polymer-derived carbon assimilation [149]. For example, PLA exposure reduced urease activity while increasing sucrase, phosphatase, and fluorescein diacetate activities, suggesting functional reorganization rather than unambiguous enhancement of soil health [150].

Long-term studies provide limited reassurance. While some report stable microbial diversity and soil organic matter after multi-year bioplastic use [151], others demonstrate microbial adaptation accompanied by altered carbon, nitrogen, and sulphur cycling and increased abundance of saprophytic and potentially pathogenic fungi [133]. Similarly, reductions in the relative abundance of genes involved in nutrient cycling after prolonged PBAT exposure [131] indicate that functional stability may mask underlying shifts in ecosystem processes [152].

Taken together, current studies demonstrate that bioplastics can induce measurable microbial responses; however, the frequent lack of direct evidence for polymer mineralization and the strong dependence on experimental context limit the ecological relevance of these findings and prevent robust conclusions on the long-term compatibility of bioplastics with soil microbial stability.

6.4. Impact on soil fauna

Soil fauna, particularly earthworms and collembolans, play a crucial role in regulating soil structure and functionality [99], but their interactions with bioplastics remain poorly characterized compared to microbial responses. Short-term studies generally report negligible effects on PBAT, PLA, and PHB particles. Adamczyk et al. (2024) reported that 11-week exposure to PBAT-MPs did not alter collembolan community composition or earthworm survival [153].

Additionally, it has been demonstrated that the ingestion of PLA and PHB particles did not cause polymer-dependent lysosomal damage or affect earthworm growth, noting that bioplastic particle size influences ingestion rates [154]. Likewise, Lu et al. (2023) found that earthworms not only tolerated 1% PLA-MPs w/w but also accelerated their degradation, likely through enhanced microbial inoculation and soil mixing [138]. Notably, earthworms exposed to Cd in soils to PLA exhibited significantly lower Cd concentrations compared to equivalent treatments with PE, indicating a potential role of PLA in mitigating heavy metal uptake [124].

However, the predominance of short-term laboratory experiments limits insights into chronic exposure scenarios, particularly under repeated applications of biodegradable mulches. Therefore, long-term consequences for soil fauna populations, trophic interactions, and ecosystem services remain largely unknown.

7. Linking biodegradation to analytical and biological insights

The environmental behavior of bioplastics in agricultural soils cannot be reliably assessed by considering degradation processes, analytical measurements, or biological responses in isolation. This work shows that, while existing studies provide valuable information about degradation mechanisms and environmental responses, a complete picture requires understanding the final fate of the carbon derived from the polymer. This is necessary to avoid overestimating degradation processes and to accurately assess long-term persistence issues. Therefore, an integrated conceptual framework is proposed that links the degradation mechanism, analytical techniques, and biological responses (Fig. 9).

The first aspect corresponds to degradation pathways. In agricultural soils, degradation progresses through erosion, fragmentation, and partial depolymerization, while complete mineralization is often uncertain or slow under realistic conditions. These pathways can generate intermediate residues, whose formation and persistence depend largely on

Fig. 9. Conceptual framework highlighting methodological and biological mismatches in bioplastic degradation studies.

the context. Standardization of degradation assessment protocols and the measurement of key parameters are also important to ensure the reproducibility and comparability of results.

The second aspect encompasses analytical methods, which determine the interpretation of biodegradation. Approaches based on mass loss or surface erosion are commonly used, while the final fate of the carbon derived from the polymer and intermediate residual compounds remains unknown.

The third aspect covers biological responses, including microbial colonization, enzymatic activity, changes in the composition of the microbial community, interactions with soil fauna, and crop responses. However, biological activity associated with bioplastics does not necessarily indicate their assimilation into soil biogeochemical cycles or functional integration into soil–crop systems.

At the centre of this framework lies knowledge about environmental fate and risk, which can only arise from the interaction between these three components. The relationships between them are bidirectional: detected fragmentation does not equate to complete mineralization; biological activity does not imply ecological functionality; and the selection of the analytical method influences the interpretation of the results. This framework provides a structured basis for interpreting current evidence and identifying limitations in existing assessment approaches.

8. Conclusions and future considerations

Applying the integrative framework proposed in this review to the existing literature indicates that biodegradability alone is an insufficient criterion to ensure the environmental safety of bioplastics in agricultural soils. Evidence from the reviewed studies shows that degradation is often partial, frequently inferred from analytical proxies rather than directly demonstrated, and commonly interpreted in biological terms without a clear link to long-term soil functionality. Consequently, biodegradable plastics may still contribute to residue accumulation and chronic exposure pathways, particularly under scenarios of repeated agricultural application.

The proposed conceptual framework highlights that current assessments may overestimate environmental performance by conflating physical disintegration with true biological mineralization and short-term biological responses with sustained ecosystem integration. These

limitations are further exacerbated by the predominance of laboratory-based studies that fail to capture the complexity and variability of agricultural soil environments. This study shows, the term *bioplastics* encompasses a highly heterogeneous group of materials, making broad generalizations about their environmental performance inappropriate.

Based on this data, different priority lines of research emerge:

1. Develop and adopt standardized methodologies to detect microplastics, transformation products and carbon flows under realistic conditions, enabling consistent comparison and robust hazard assessment.
2. Evaluate environmental behavior and hazards at the level of individual polymers and formulations, considering chemical structure and additives in realistic agricultural scenarios.
3. Conduct multi-season experiments with repeated applications to assess accumulation, soil structural effects, ecosystem impacts, and crop performance over time.
4. Investigate microbial or enzymatic strategies to accelerate degradation, assessing impacts on carbon cycling, soil structure, and crop productivity.
5. Design bioplastics with degradation kinetics aligned to crop growth and seasonal variability, ensuring functional performance and minimal accumulation in soils.

Adopting this integrative, hazard- and function-oriented framework will consolidate bioplastics as a sustainable, ecologically compatible alternative to conventional plastics in agroecosystems.

Environmental implication

This review promotes environmental sustainability by explaining how bioplastics behave, change, and interact within agricultural soils under real-world conditions. By defining key environmental factors that control degradation and highlighting important methodological gaps, the review enhances the ability to predict the formation and fate of biomicroplastics. This work also assesses responses in soil, crops, and microbiomes, demonstrating when bioplastics may pose risks and when they can support sustainable farming. Overall, this study provides the scientific knowledge needed to promote safer bioplastic use and reduce hazard microplastic pollution in agriculture.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, M.A-D., M.R., R.P., and J.A.P.; data curation, M.A-D., M.R., R.P., and J.A.P.; formal analysis, M.A-D., M.R., R.P., and J.A.P.; writing—original draft preparation, M.A-D.; writing—review and editing, M.A-D., M.R., R.P., and J.A.P.; supervision, M.A-D., M.R., R.P., and J.A.P.; funding acquisition, M.R., R.P., and J.A.P. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Margarita Ros: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Rosa Penalver:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **José Antonio Pascual:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Marina Alcaraz-Dólera:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2026.141783](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2026.141783).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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